

Stress tolerance—adverse soils

Germination and growth of some salt-resistant selections in high salt concentration solutions

J. Ahmed and S. Gupta, *Rice Research Station, Chinsurah 712102, West Bengal, India*

In coastal areas of West Bengal, most ricelands are below the high tide level. Although earthen embankments prevent tidewater from entering the fields, there are chances for an increase in salinity of seedbeds. Seawater often enters the plots through lateral seepage or through upward percolation from nearby drainage channels, riverines, or estuaries. This hampers germination and seedling growth. Salinity increases are more pronounced when rain is scanty or erratic.

We evaluated three promising selections for coastal tidal wetlands and Hamilton, an improved selection from local cultivar Nona Bokra, under high salt concentrations in the laboratory (see table).

Germination was tested by the glass plate method. Two 25-seed sets/line were immersed in distilled water and salt solutions of 5, 10, and 15 dS/m.

The solutions were prepared by dissolving sodium chloride, calcium chloride, and sodium sulfate at 7:2:1 to obtain the derived estimates of electrical conductivity values.

Germinated seeds were counted 10 d after immersion and root length, seedling height, and seedling dry weight measured.

Overall, germination decreased with an

increase in salt concentration. But the loss of germination was much slower in IR51194-CN930-44-16-B. Germination was significant even at 10 dS/m.

Root length was also severely affected at 15 dS/m in all test entries except IR51194-CN930-44-16-B.

Rate of shoot growth was not much affected, except in Hamilton. Dry matter accumulation also was not much affected. Differences in rate of dry matter accumulation, however, were conspicuous. □

Effect of salt concentration on seed germination and seedling characters of 4 rice entries.

Entry	Treatment (dS/m)	Mean germination (%)	Root length (cm)			Seedling height (cm)			Dry weight (g) of 100 seedlings (mean × 100)
			Mean	±	SD	Mean	±	SD	
IR4630-22-5-1-3/1 -CN-1	Control	72	4.30	1.131	4.26	2.878	1.66		
	5	32	2.30	1.389	4.07	0.750	1.45		
	10	12	3.34	1.333	3.98	1.374	1.72		
	15	4	2.74	1.146	4.08	1.616	1.62		
IR51194-CN930-44-16-B	Control	66	2.33	0.533	5.13	0.883	0.95		
	5	64	3.04	2.020	4.12	1.630	0.59		
	10	48	2.84	2.418	4.82	2.586	1.40		
	15	40	4.89	0.448	5.99	1.227	1.31		
IR13198-66-2-CN939-2-1	Control	65	5.10	3.690	4.46	2.832	1.77		
	5	55	4.68	2.124	4.46	1.326	2.09		
	10	15	6.50	1.000	3.82	0.832	1.86		
	15	5	2.75	-	5.75	-	1.17		
Hamilton	Control	88	3.90	1.482	8.33	3.474	1.79		
	5	60	10.94	2.225	12.04	2.586	1.63		
	10	76	4.40	2.227	11.05	1.640	1.93		
	15	8	0.75	-	4.75	-	1.75		

Effect of abscisic acid (ABA) application on salt tolerance of rice varieties

J. S. Bohra, *Agronomy Department, Institute of Agricultural Sciences, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi 221005, India*; and K. Doffling, *Institute of General Botany, University of Hamburg, Germany*

Cation ratios, mainly the K:Na ratio, play a vital role in reducing rice growth and yield under saline conditions. We studied the effect of applying ABA on dry matter accumulation and cation concentrations and ratios.

The experiment in the phytotron

involved IR28 (salt-sensitive), IR20 (semitolerant), and Pokkali (tolerant); salinity levels of EC 10 and 15 dS/m; without ABA and with five weekly sprayings of ABA at 10^{-4} mol/liter, starting from 17 d after sowing (DAS). The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design with three replications.

Earthen pots were filled with 2.5 kg air-dried soil and puddled. Ten seeds were sown/pot. At 12 DAS, plants were thinned to three/pot.

Salinity treatments beginning 18 DAS were one irrigation/wk with 300 ml NaCl solution. On other days, pots were irrigated with plain water. Three pots of each variety were not treated.

Temperature in the growth chamber was maintained at 30/25 °C day/night, 12 h photoperiod, and 70-80% relative humidity.

Plants were harvested 48 DAS. Cation concentrations were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometry (AAS).

ABA application significantly increased shoot dry weight and K:Na ratio in IR28 and IR20; it did not affect Pokkali (see table). K and Na concentrations in shoots were reduced 3.1% in IR28 and 29.7% in IR20. The K:Na ratio increased 17.7%. The benefit may be attributed to a lower transpiration rate, with a consequent reduced flux of Na through the root.